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Design and Fabrication of Super Heater used in Boiling System

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ABSTRACT

Super heater is one of the integral parts of the boiler. Design of super heater is modified compared to previous super heater to improve steam output. In huge power plants super heater have two stages, in between this two stages de-super heater are used. The main function of de- super heater is to control the temperature of the steam by sprinkling the water drops on its outer surface which gets contact to the flue gases. This temperature will be controlled without any losses de-super heater can only be used in large power plants as it occupies huge space and also expensive. In this project according to design procedure, fabrication of damper in super heater chamber in made which works manually and acts as d-super heater, which control the director of the flue gases. This manual operation is comparatively economical and occupies less space than de-super heater. The operation of the damper in super heater chamber is as follows: by inserting the damper in super heater chamber diverts the flue gases as this controls the heat from the gases touching the super heater tubes. By opening the damper flue gases are allowed to super heater tubes. By this tube failure is controlled and efficiency of the super heater increased. In power industries, steam is used to perform mechanical work, such as driving a turbine, and also as a heat transfer fluid. Both functions are accomplished with steam properties at opposite ends dry superheated steam at high end, while de-superheated steam near its saturation point at the low end. Introduction of De-superheater can effectively improve the thermal efficiency of heat transfer processes by allowing the usage of steam at its saturation point, to control unintentional superheat from reducing the pressure of steam, to protect the boiler equipment and piping from high temperatures and pressures.

Keywords: super heater, boiler, design, temperature

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Boiling systems such as boilers are prime source of thermal energy in most industrial units and thermal energy is one of the very important requirements for many industries. Boiler is an enclosed vessel that provides a means for combustion heat to be transferred into water until it becomes heated water or steam (Krishanet *al.*, 2014). The steam or hot fluid is then circulated out of the boiler for use in various process or heating applications (Durkin, 2006). The steam boiler has very important application in the palm oil mill. It supplies the steam and heating for the palm oil production, such as in sterilizer section, digester section, clarification section, and oil drying system. But in the different section, the functions are different (Ahmad, 2006; Afrieldo, 2021).

Boilers have a very important role in the continuity of the performance of a palm oil mill, in other words, it can be referred to as the heart of a palm oil mill. The function of the boiler is to produce steam which is used for the needs of the palm oil mill process, and to generate electricity for the needs of the oil mill and employee housing around the oil mill (Afrieldo, 2021). Oil mill equipment in the form of a boiler system is a very important asset for the company. The boiler here has an important role in the steam production process, where this steam will later be used to drive a steam turbine as a producer of electrical energy for oil mill needs and the turbine output steam is used for the boiling process (sterilizer) and oil purification process (clarification). The steam boiler system comprises of fuel system, feed water system and steam system (Afrieldo, 2021; Bujak, 2009; Ahmad, 2006). The fuel system includes all equipment used to provide fuel to generate the necessary heat. The equipment required in the fuel system depends on the type of fuel used in the system. Steam is produced in boiler using various types of fuels such as coal, fuel oil, natural gas, biogas etc. (Elshamy, 2006; Amit, 2012; Chetanet al., 2013). The feed water system provides water to the boiler and regulates it automatically to meet the steam demand. Various valves provide access for maintenance and repair. The steam system collects and controls the steam produced in the boiler. Steam is directed through a piping system to the point of use. Throughout the system, steam pressure is regulated using valves and checked with steam pressure gauges. Boiler operation is energy intensive; hence the performance of the boiler is pertinent for reduced operating cost (Saiduret al., 2009). The performance of boiler is expressed as efficiency of boiler which is the ratio of output energy (amount of heat used for the generation of steam) to the input energy (amount of heat supplied). The percentage of useful energy input used in the generated heat is indicative of the boiler efficiency. Equivalent evaporation (evaporation ratio) is also used to compare the performance of boilers when the operating conditions are different for various boilers (Khandare, 2008). The performance of boilers depends on several factors such as combustion efficiency, maintenance, quality of water, quantity of excess air, temperature of flue gas, heat loss, operating conditions of boilers etc (Carpenter et al., 2008). The combustion efficiency of any boiler is an important factor as it directly controls the fuel consumption.

The thermodynamic performance of the boiler, such as the boiler thermal efficiency and evaporation ratio reduces with time, due to poor combustion, heat transfer fouling and poor operation and maintenance (Egeonu et al., 2015). Deterioration of fuel quality and water quality also leads to poor performance of boiler. Evaluating the thermodynamic performance of boiler such as the boiler efficiency helps us to find out how far the boiler efficiency drifts away from the optimal efficiency and any observed abnormal deviations could therefore be investigated to pinpoint the problematic area for necessary corrective action. The British Standard BS845: 1987 describes the methods and conditions under which a boiler should be tested to determine its efficiency (ABMA, 2020; BS 845, 1987). For the testing to be done, the boiler should be operated under steady load conditions (generally full load) for a period of one hour after which readings would be taken during the next hour of steady operation to enable the efficiency to be calculated. The efficiency of a boiler is quoted as the percentage of useful heat available, expressed as a percentage of the total energy potentially available by burning the fuel (Ukpaka et al., 2019). This is expressed on the basis of gross calorific value (GCV). Basically, boiler efficiency can be evaluated by either the direct or indirect method. In the direct method, the energy gain of the working fluid (water and steam) is compared with the energy content of the boiler fuel. This is also known as 'input-output method' due to the fact that it needs only the useful output (steam) and the heat input (i.e. fuel) for evaluating the thermal efficiency. In the indirect method: the efficiency is the difference between the losses and the energy input (Szega&Czyż, 2019; Ukpaka et al., 2019). A boiler system in an oil mill must function efficiently under specified and optimal operating conditions in order to ensure the continuous operation of the palm oil mill for optimal productivity.

A superheater is a vital part of the boiler system that is used to increase the overall efficiency of a thermal power plant. More specifically, it is a device which converts wet steam (saturated steam) into dry steam as dry steam contains more thermal energy. However, my focus in this research project is the fabrication of damper in super heater chamber which works manually and acts as de-super heater

A desuperheater in a boiler is a device used to reduce the temperature of superheated steam. It works by injecting a controlled amount of water into the superheated steam, which causes the steam to lose some of its heat as it evaporates the water. This process helps to maintain the desired temperature and prevents the steam from causing damage to downstream equipment. The desuperheater plays a crucial role in controlling the temperature of steam in industrial processes and power generation.

De-superheating is the process of reducing the temperature of the superheated steam to its saturation point. The de-superheater is used to reduce the temperature of steam generated by high pressure/temperature boilers to the level required in process operation. The primary function of a desuperheater is to lower the temperature of superheated steam & vapour.

The primary function of a desuperheater water heater is to minimize the temperature of superheated gas and other vapors. This temperature reduction is achieved by the process vapor being brought into direct contact with a liquid such as water. Figure 1.1 shows the pictorial diagram of a typical superheater in a boiling system.

Figure 1.1: A typical Steam Superheater of a Boiling System (Boiler)

Desuperheating is the process by which superheated steam is restored to its saturated state, or the superheat temperature is reduced. Most desuperheaters used to restore the saturated state produce discharge temperatures approaching saturation (typically to within 3°C of the saturation temperature as a minimum). Designs for discharge temperatures in excess of 3°C above saturation are also possible and often used.

There are basically two broad types of desuperheater:

Indirect contact type - The medium used to cool the superheated steam does not come into direct contact with it. A cooler liquid or gas may be employed as the cooling medium, for example, the surrounding air. Examples of this type of desuperheater are shell and tube heat exchangers.

Here the superheated steam is supplied to one side of the heat exchanger and a cooler medium is supplied to the other side. As the superheated steam passes through the heat exchanger, heat is lost from the steam, and gained by the cooling medium.

The temperature of the desuperheater steam could be controlled by either the inlet superheated steam pressure or the flowrate of the cooling water. Control of the superheated steam flow for this purpose is not normally practical and most systems adjust the flow of the cooling medium.

Direct contact type - The medium used to cool the superheated steam comes into direct contact with it. In most cases, the cooling medium is the same fluid as the vapour to be desuperheated, but in the liquid state. For example, in the case of steam desuperheaters, water is used. A typical direct contact desuperheating station is shown in Figure 15.1.3.

When the desuperheater is operational, a measured amount of water is added to the superheated steam via a mixing arrangement within the desuperheater. As it enters the desuperheater, the cooling water evaporates by absorbing heat from the superheated steam. Consequently, the temperature of the steam is reduced.

Control of the amount of water to be added is usually achieved by measuring the temperature of the steam downstream of the desuperheater. The set temperature of the desuperheated steam would typically be 3°C above that at saturation. Therefore, in such arrangements the inlet pressure of the superheated steam should be kept constant.

1.1.1 Principle of Operation

All de-superheater operate on the same principle. Water (usually condensate), is introduced into the process line and thus comes into direct contact with the superheated steam. That is, the process of adding water to steam to lower its temperature is known as de-superheating and the device used is called as de-superheater. Evaporation of the water reduces the steam temperature. The outlet steam temperature is controlled by the quantity of water that is evaporated. This minimizes the time of the suspension of the water particles in the steam so that all the water is evaporated and none falls to the inside walls of the pipe work. A typical direct contact desuperheating station is as shown in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: A typical Direct Contact Desuperheating Station

1.1.2 Function of a Damper in a Boiler System

A damper in a boiler is used to control the flow of air and combustion gases into and out of the boiler. It helps regulate the combustion process by adjusting the amount of air that enters the boiler, which in turn affects the efficiency and performance of the boiler. By controlling the airflow, the damper helps maintain the proper balance of oxygen and fuel for combustion, ensuring safe and efficient operation of the boiler. They are used to regulate mechanical draft and keep a heating system running safely and optimally. With a multiple boiler system, manual dampers are an ideal choice because they can be adjusted at each boiler and are therefore great for keeping the draft constant throughout a stack. The schematic and pictorial diagram of a typical damper component in a boiler system is shown in Figures 1.2 and 1.3 respectively.

Figure 1.3: Schematic Diagram of a Typical Damper Component in Boiler System

Figure 1.4: Pictorial diagram of a Typical Damper of a Boiler

1.2 Statement of the Problem

A mechanical draft is created by blowers and fans as opposed to environmental elements, commonly referred to as natural draft. Dampers are used to regulate mechanical draft and keep a heating system running safely and optimally. With a multiple boiler system, manual dampers are an ideal choice because they can be adjusted at each boiler and are therefore great for keeping the draft constant throughout a stack. With no manual dampers in place, it is actually very difficult to maintain consistency because as the draft drops off the further you move away from a chimney stack. They are also great for adjusting airflow when external conditions affect draft. Therefore, as long as manual dampers are utilized properly, they are completely acceptable and suitable for mechanical draft applications.

1.3 Aim of the Study

The aim of this research work is to keep the heating system in a boiler running safe and optimally by using a manually fabricated damper as a desuperheater.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this research include to:

- i. Fabricate a manual damper in a superheater.
- ii. Using the fabricated manual damper as a desuperheater in keeping the draft constant throughout a stack in the boiler system.
- iii. Using the fabricated damper in the adjustment of airflow when external conditions affect draft.
- iv. Using the fabricated damper to control the flow of air and combustion gases into and out of the boiler.
- v. Using the fabricated damper to help regulate the combustion process by adjusting the amount of air that enters the boiler, this in turn affects the efficiency and performance of the boiler.

1.5 Scope of the Study

In order to achieve the set of objectives of the research work, the scope of this research was limited to:

- i. The fabrication of a manual damper in a superheater which acts as a desuperheater in a boiler system.
- ii. The function of manual dampers as desuperheaters in a boiler system.
- iii. The study of the boiler system in Nigerian Bottling Company (NBC) Plc plant, Trans-Amadi, Port Harcourt, Rivers state.

MATERIALS

Basic Design Requirements

Carbon steel is steels with carbon content up to 2.1% by weight. The term “carbon steel” may also be used in reference to steel which is not stainless steel; in this use carbon steel may include alloy steels. As the carbon percentage content rises, steel has the ability to become harder and stronger through heat treating; however, it becomes less ductile. Regardless of the heat treatment, higher carbon content reduces weldability. In carbon steels, the higher carbon content lowers the melting point.

- i. Compliance with the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code.
- ii. Compliance with required safety and installation Codes.
- iii. The ability to meet the required efficiency and other performance standards.
- iv. Compliance with the requirements of the National Board of Boiler and Pressure Vessel Inspections.

Design Specification

Dampers in the paths of air and flue gas work on flow streams in the following four ways:

- i. Isolation
- ii. Control
- iii. Diversion
- iv. Non-return

All boiler dampers used as desuperheaters are fabricated from sheet steel to the required sizes and specifications. There are four types of dampers.

- i. Louver or flap-type dampers for control and isolation duties. However, they cannot provide a tight shutoff.
- ii. Guillotine dampers for isolation duty. Even 100% shutoff is achievable.
- iii. Diverter dampers for diverting the flow as in HRSG bypass.
- iv. Non-return flap dampers for preventing flow in reverse direction, such as a weather damper in the HRSG stack.

3.1.3 Design Consideration for Material Selection

For an intelligent design to be done, the knowledge of the materials available as well as the properties they possess is very important. For the selection of the proper material to be used for the design of the damper, I shall consider

the factors which affect the choice of material selected and used for design and there reasons. Factors considered are:

- i. Suitability of the material for the working conditions in service, considering characteristics such as; appearance, thermal conductivity, rate of emissivity, strength, stiffness, creep, etc.
- ii. Availability of the material: the ease at which the materials are seen or purchased in the market.
- iii. Workability of the material: considering possible methods of processing material selected into desired shape such as; weldability, machinability, formability, and workability.
- iv. Expected load or force as well as adequate strength in conformity so as to function satisfactorily without failure.
- v. Cost of the material (economic consideration).

However, the main material used for the fabrication of the damper is mild steel because it is less expensive than other metals.

Components of the Boiler system in Nigerian Bottling Company (NBC) Plc

The main component parts of the boiler in the Nigerian Bottling Company (NBC) Plc production plant are as follows:

- i. Combustion Chamber/Firebox
- ii. Heat Exchanger
- iii. Expansion tank
- iv. Burner
- v. Backflow Valve
- vi. Super heater
- vii. Economiser
- viii. Air preheater
- ix. Feed water pump
- x. Chemney
- xi. Supply lines
- xii. Return lines

Combustion Chamber/Firebox

The burner creates combustion in this chamber that heats the heat exchanger up to several hundred degrees. The fuel that is burned in this chamber varies. Kerosene, heating oil, and liquid propane are the most common fuel sources used in the combustion chamber of the boilers. The firebox or the combustion chamber is usually made of cast iron to withstand the heat and the pressure of the process inside. The process increases the temperature inside the chamber up to several hundred degrees in a really short time so the used materials should be suitable for such a condition.

i. Heat Exchanger

The combustion created in the firebox, creates a heat that's transferred by the heat exchanger to heat the fluid up in the tank. This heat exchanger carries the produced heat to the fluid without any direct contact with the water.

ii. Expansion tank

Another item in the list of different parts of boilers is expansion tank; this small tank is responsible for protecting the boiler from excessive pressure and ensures its safety along the process.

iii. Burner

One of the most important parts of boiler is the burner which is where the mixing of the air with the fuel source happens, resulting in the combustion which provides the necessary heat to heat up the fluid. They are responsible for initiating the combustion reaction in the system with the electronic signal of the thermostats to the burner. This signal informs the system when there's a need to produce heat. The burner uses the fuel pumped from an outside source with a filter mechanism. There's a nozzle designed on the burner to turn this fuel into the spray and ignites it initiate the combustion inside the firebox.

iv. Backflow Valve

Backflow valve acts as a safety unit, allowing the flow of the fluid only in a single direction.

v. Super heater

The function of superheater in in the industrial boiler analyzed in this study is to increase the overall efficiency of the boiler system.

vi. Economizer

The economizer is the component in the boiler which is used to achieve greater energy efficiency by using outside air to help control indoor temperatures.

vii. Air Preheater

The function of the air preheater is to recover the heat from the boiler flue gas which increases the thermal efficiency of the boiler by reducing the useful heat lost in the flue gas.

viii. Feed water pump

This component is used to produce steam from the boiler. It is a crucial component of the boiler system.

ix. Chimney

This is used to safely remove the combustion gases and smoke produced during burning fuel in the boiler.

x. Supply lines

These parts of boiler are pipes that are responsible for delivering the heated stream of fluid to the distribution points in the boiler.

xi. Return lines

Return lines are responsible for bringing the cooled fluid or the cooled steam (which changes its state back to its liquid form) back to the boiler to heat it up again.

The steam boiler in Nigerian Bottling Company (NBC) Plc (NBC, 2006a):

- (a) Feed water unit which consists of: two (2) deaerator, where dissolved oxygen and other gases are removed to prevent corrosion damage in the steam system and to increase the feed water temperature as well (The total design capacity of each of the deaerator is 640tonnes/h) as well as five (5) feed water (centrifugal) pumps which transports feed water to the boiler. The feed water pump system consists of two high pressure (HP) boiler feed water pump, two low pressure (LP) boiler feed water pumps and one start up boiler feed water pump. The following is the list of design parameters of boiler feed water pump:

Pump Type	=	Centrifugal pump
Capacity	=	24 tonnes/h for boilers and 18tonnes/h for process water.
Suction pressure	=	0.24MPa
Discharge pressure	=	5.93MPa
Feed water (FW) temperature	=	125°C

The feed water unit also comprises of water heater (70E01A, B) which acts as preheater of the boiler feed water. It has the following design parameters:

Capacity	=	24tonnes/h
Feed water (FW) temperature	=	Inlet 125°C Outlet 140°C

- (b) The NBC manufacturing plant is designed with Liquefied Petroleum Gas/Natural Gas fired boiler which produces steam for production, such as in sterilizer section, digester section, clarification section, and oil drying system and fully automatic with temperature control. The following is the list of design parameters of boiler:

Rated feed water temperature	=	105°C (378K)
Rated working pressure	=	0.5MPa (5bars)
Rated steam output	=	1tonnes/h (0.3kg/s)
Rated steam temperature	=	195°C (468K)
Fuel	=	LNG/LPG
Fuel consumption rate	=	70.1m ³ /h (0.038kg/s)

Figure 3.1: A typical Boiler System in NBC Plc

Design of Superheater in Boiling System (Boiler)

In designing a superheater, several factors such as tube size, number of streams carrying the steam flow, tube spacing, gas mass velocity, etc., are selected based on experience. Fig 3.2 and Fig 3.3 shows a typical flow chart of a superheater subsystem of a boiler respectively.

Figure 3.2 Shows a Typical Flow Chart of a Superheater Subsystem of a Boiler

- 1--- superheater spray valve 2---superheater spray 3---feedwater valve
 4---economiser 5---drum

Figure 3.3 Shows a Typical Flow Chart of a Superheater Subsystem of a Boiler

Damper Construction

When high amount of flue gases hits the superheater tubes, if there is no steam flow in the superheater then tubes gets damaged or melted. So, to prevent this melting or corrosion of superheater tubes manual damper is used instead of desuperheater. The manual damper is chosen because its cost is less than desuperheater, and the remaining properties are the same as strong as desuperheater. Flue gases are allowed to flow from the combustion chamber to the superheater tubes directly because it is places directly above the combustion chamber. If there is no steam flow in the superheater tubes, then damper is inserted into the superheater to cover the entire superheater tubes. This damper is inserted from left side of superheater through a small hole. This damper is made up of mild steel material, because its capacity to handle the temperature of flue gases is more and also its cost is very less than other metals.

This damper would handle flue gases, and has a flow rate of 105 meter cubic per seconds (m³/sec), a design temperature of 399°C, an inlet pressure of 14000 Pascal (pa), and shut off pressure of 21000 Pascal (pa). Seal design for this damper was a hi-performance bolted metal step seat. The outer diameter of the damper is 0.2032m weighing 70.05 x 10⁵ N/m², and the material thickness is 0.01905m respectively.

In process and after construction testing was extensive, with this damper undergoing a series of NDE tests including radiography of body seam, hardness testing of cobalt hard-faced surfaces, and PMI on all alloy materials. Other testing includes hydrostatic test of body assemblies, a 24-hour heat stroke test at design temperature, and seat leakage testing

Table 3.1: TTD Calculation: Overall Heat Transfer Coefficient” U” Calculation On Cleanliness Factor

S/NO	DESCRIPTION	SYMBOL	VALUE	UNIT
1.	Uncorrected heat transfer coefficient	U ₁	1674.873	Kcal/m ² h ⁰ C
2.	Inlet water temperature correction factor	F _w	0.823	
3.	Tube material & gauge correction factor	F _m	0.9	
4.	Cleanliness factor	F _c	0.6528	
5.	Overall heat transfer co-efficient= U=U ₁ ×F _w × F _m × F _c	U	809.849	

Table 3.2: Surface Area Calculation of Superheater of the Boiler in the Production Plant (NBC Plc, 2006a)

S/NO	DESCRIPTION	SYMBOL	VALUE	UNIT
1.	Heat to be supplied to super heater	Q	1373.205	Kcal/hr
2.	Overall heat transfer co-efficient	U	809.85	Kcal/m ² h
3.	Terminal temperature difference	TTD	30.00	°C
4.	Total area required=Q/(U×TTD)	A	0.06	m ²

Method of Evaluating Boiler’s Thermodynamic Performance in Production Plant

In analyzing the collected boiler operating data, the energy and exergy analytical method were selected and applied for the performance evaluation of the boiler system in the production plant. In order to calculate the energy transfer in the boiler system from the energy source and energy efficiency of the boiler the energy analytical method, based on the first law of thermodynamics was applied. The exergy analytical method was applied to analyze the exergy destruction and exergy efficiency of the boiler based on the second law of thermodynamics. In the analysis, MATLAB computer program and SPSS computer software was employed to analyze the result data of the energy efficiency, exergy destruction and exergy efficiency of the boiler system.

Thermodynamic Analytical Model of the Boiler Operation

The operations of boiler obey the first and second laws of thermodynamics which states that, energy can neither be created nor destroyed, but it can be transformed or transferred from one form to another for the first law and that as energy is transferred or transformed, more and more of the transferred/transformed energy is wasted or lost (Yunus & Michael, 2018). The laws of thermodynamics are used to determine the theoretical limits for the energy and exergy performance of mostly used engineering systems such as heat engines, heat pump and steam generators (like steam boilers). The heat energy flow in a steam boiler is shown in the line diagram of Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.4: Heat Flow during the Boiler System Operation (Nishant et al., 2018).

The steady flow energy equation in steam boiler as shown in Figure 3.1 is given as:

$$\dot{Q} - \dot{W} = \dot{m} \left[(h_2 - h_1) + \frac{1}{2}(c_2^2 - c_1^2) + g(z_2 - z_1) \right] \tag{3.1}$$

where \dot{Q} = heat input (kW)

- \dot{W} = work output (kW)
- \dot{m} = mass flow rate of water/mass of water supplied per unit time (kg/s)
- h_2 = specific enthalpy of the fluid at point 2/exit/outlet (kJ/kg)
- h_1 = specific enthalpy of the fluid at point 1/entry/inlet (kJ/kg)
- c_2 = velocity at point 2/exit/outlet (m/s)
- c_1 = velocity at point 1/entry/inlet (m/s)
- g = gravitational acceleration (m/s²)
- z_2 = height of the fluid at point 2/exit/outlet (m)
- z_1 = height of the fluid at point 1/entry/inlet (m)

Also, for the mass flow rate per unit time, the unit of the terms of both sides of the equations is now watts (w) or kilowatts (kW), which is the energy per unit time of power.

Let us follow the events which occur as heat is transferred to the water in a boiler system while the pressure is kept constant. The initial state of the system is represented as point 1 on the temperature-volume as shown in Figure 3.2. It must be emphasised that the changes in volume as represented in Figure 3.2 are not drawn to scale.

**Figure 3.5: T-V Diagram for Boiler Water System
(Yunus & Michael, 2018)**

First the temperature rises and liquid water expands in volume until a temperature of about 100°C (373K) is reached at point 2 as indicated by the line 1-2. The heat transferred between points 1 and 2 is referred to as sensible heat because it brings about change in temperature. At point 2, boiling occurs. The temperature remains constant until all the liquid is vaporized at point 3. There is a large increase in volume during this process. The heat required in this case is called the latent heat of vaporization. When vaporization is complete, the temperature rises once again with volume. This is represented by the line 3-4. The steam is then said to be superheated. The lines 1, 2, 3 and 4 for water are constant pressure lines or isobars. The expansion of a vapour per degree rise in temperature is usually higher than that of a liquid or even a solid of the same substance.

The summary of changes in behaviour of water in a boiler system at constant pressure is as follows:

- 1 – 2 Increase in temperature and volume of the liquid water from point 1 to 2 causes the liquid water to become saturated at point 2 where boiling commences.
- 2 – 3 Constant temperature and increase in the volume of the saturated water from point 2 to 3 causes the saturated water to become a two phase mixture at saturated liquid water and vapour. Vapour becomes saturated at point 3 when water has completely vaporized
- 3 – 4 Increase in temperature and volume of the saturated vapour (completely vaporized water) from point 3 to 4 causes the mixture to become superheated vapour at point 4.

According to the T-V diagram shown in Figure 3.2, the actual heat supplied to the water per unit time in the boiler system at point 1 to become saturated at point 2 where boiling commences \dot{Q}_{1-2} is obtained from the relation (Yunus & Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{Q}_{1-2} = \dot{m} c_p (t_2 - t_1) \tag{3.2}$$

- where \dot{m} = mass flow rate of water/mass of water supplied per unit time (kg/s)
- c_p = specific heat capacity of water at constant pressure (kJ/kgK)
- t_2 = temperature of the fluid at point 2 (K)
- t_1 = temperature of the fluid at point 1 (K)

If the specific heat capacity of water at constant pressure is not given then, \dot{Q}_{1-2} is obtained from the relation (Yunus & Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{Q}_{1-2} = \dot{m}(h_2 - h_1) \tag{3.3}$$

- where h_2 = enthalpy of the fluid at point 2 (kJ/kg)
- h_1 = enthalpy of the fluid at point 1 (kJ/kg)

The saturated liquid water is taken to a saturated vapour at constant temperature. Dryness fraction changes from 0 to

1. The actual heat added at this section per unit time from point 2 to point 3, \dot{Q}_{2-3} is obtained from the relation (Yunus & Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{Q}_{2-3} = \dot{m}(h_3 - h_2) \tag{3.4}$$

- where h_3 = enthalpy of the fluid at point 3 (kJ/kg)
- h_2 = enthalpy of the fluid at point 2 (kJ/kg)

Thirdly, the saturated vapour is superheated. The actual heat added in this section per unit time \dot{Q}_{3-4} is given by (Yunus& Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{Q}_{3-4} = \dot{m}(h_4 - h_3) \quad (3.5)$$

where h_4 = enthalpy of the fluid at point 4 (kJ/kg)

h_3 = enthalpy of the fluid at point 3 (kJ/kg)

Therefore, the total actual heat transferred to the fluid (water) in the boiler per unit time (\dot{Q}_B) is:

$$\dot{Q}_B = \dot{Q}_{12} + \dot{Q}_{23} + \dot{Q}_{34} \quad (3.6)$$

Energy Analysis

Energy analysis is done on the boiler through the first law of thermodynamics. Figure 3.3 is used to determine the energy transfer in the boiler from the energy source into steam and energy efficiency of the boiler.

Figure 3.4: Schematic of Energy Transfer

i. Energy Transfer

The energy transfer in the boiler (\dot{Q}_B) from the energy source into the working fluid is express in kilowatt (kW)

and is given as (Yunus& Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{Q}_B = \dot{m}(h_b - h_a) \quad (3.7)$$

where \dot{m} = mass flow rate of steam (kg/s),

h_b = enthalpy of superheated steam leaving the boiler at point b (kJ/kg)

h_a = enthalpy of feed water entering the boiler at point a (kJ/kg)

ii. Energy Source

The energy source in the boiler (\dot{Q}_S) is the energy from the liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) which is used to fire the boiler expressed in kilowatt (kW) and is given as (Yunus& Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{Q}_S = \dot{m}_{LPG} CV_{LPG} \tag{3.8}$$

where \dot{m}_{LPG} = mass flow rate of the LPG (kg/s),

CV_{LPG} = calorific value of LPG (kJ/kg)

iii. Energy Efficiency

Energy efficiency of the boiler (η_B) is the percentage of heat input that is effectively utilized to generate steam. From Figure 3.4 it is given as (Yunus& Michael, 2018):

$$\eta_B = \frac{\dot{Q}_B}{\dot{Q}_S} \tag{3.9}$$

where \dot{Q}_B = energy transfer in the boiler (kW)

\dot{Q}_S = energy source in the boiler (kW)

Exergy Analysis

Exergy analysis is a tool for analyzing the exergy destruction and exergy efficiency through the second law of thermodynamics (Yunus& Michael, 2018). From Figure 3.4, the exergies entering the boiler are the exergy of feed water and thermal exergy, while the exergy leaving the boiler is exergy of steam.

Figure 3.6: Schematic of Exergy Transfer

i. Exergy of Feed-water entering the Boiler

The exergy of feed-water entering the boiler (\dot{E}_a) is expressed in kilowatts (kW) and is given as (Yunus& Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{E}_a = \dot{m}C_{pw} \left[(T_a - T_o) - T_o \ln\left(\frac{T_a}{T_o}\right) \right] \quad (3.10)$$

where \dot{m} = mass flow rate of feed-water (kg/s),
 C_{pw} = specific capacity of feed-water entering the boiler at point a (kJ/kgK)
 T_a = temperature of feed water entering the boiler at point a (K)
 T_o = ambient temperature (K). At the pressure and temperature of the surrounding (P_o) is 1 bar and (T_o)is 298K, the water is slightly compressed liquid, and the properties of the water are essentially equal to those for saturated liquid at 298k(Yunus& Michael, 2018).

ii. Thermal Exergy Entering the Boiler

At high boiler temperature, exergy is destroyed as a result of entropy generation and transfer of heat to the environment which acts as a cold reservoir. The thermal exergy associated with the heat transfer to the boiler from heat source (\dot{E}_s) is expressed in kilowatt (kW) and is given as (Yunus& Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{E}_s = \left(1 - \frac{T_o}{T_b} \right) \dot{Q}_s \quad (3.11)$$

where T_b = temperature of steam leaving the boiler at point b (K)

iii. Exergy of Steam Leaving the Boiler

Exergy of steam leaving the boiler (\dot{E}_b) is expressed in kilowatts (kW) and is given as (Yunus& Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{E}_b = \dot{m}[(h_b - h_o) - T_o(S_b - S_o)] \quad (3.12)$$

where h_b = enthalpy of superheated steam leaving the boiler at point b (kJ/kgK)
 h_o = enthalpy of steam at dead state (kJ/kgK)
 S_b = entropy of steam leaving the boiler at point b (kJ/kgK)
 S_o = entropy of steam at dead state (kJ/kgK)

iv. Exergy Destruction in the Boiler

Exergy destruction is a measure of the thermodynamic inefficiencies within the boiler. It is calculated as the difference between the inlet and outlet exergies in the forms of heat, work, and material as well as the change of the exergy stored. From Figure 3.4, the exergy destruction in the boiler (\dot{E}_{DB}) is expressed in kilowatts (kW) and is given by (Yunus& Michael, 2018):

$$\dot{E}_{DB} = (\dot{E}_a + \dot{E}_s) - \dot{E}_b \tag{3.13}$$

where \dot{E}_a = the inlet heat supplied to the boiler

\dot{E}_s = the heat source

\dot{E}_b = the outlet heat from the boiler

v. Exergy Efficiency of the Boiler

Exergy efficiency is the ration of the total exergy leaving the boiler to the total exergy entering (Yunus& Michael, 2018) and it is given as:

$$\zeta_B = 1 - \frac{\dot{E}_{DB}}{\dot{E}_b + \dot{E}_s} \tag{3.14}$$

where \dot{E}_b = the outlet heat from the boiler

\dot{E}_s = the heat source

Combustion Analysis

Combustion analysis is part of a process intended to improve fuel economy, reduce undesirable exhaust emissions and improve safety of the boiler. One of the metric used in combustion analysis is combustion efficiency (Yunus& Michael, 2018).

i. Combustion Efficiency of the Boiler

The combustion efficiency refers to the optimum balance of air to fuel in the combustion process. It is the dry volume concentration of CO₂ in parts per million (ppm) for volume given as (Bruce, 2011).

$$CE = \left[\frac{CO_2}{(CO_2 + CO)} \right] \times 100 \tag{3.15}$$

where CO₂ = the dry column concentration of CO₂

CO = the dry column concentration of CO

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hydrostatic Testing of Damper

A hydrostatic test was conducted on superheater elements and damper elements respectively. 15kgs of pressurized water was applied to determine if there were any leaks. This water in the evaporator chamber gets converted into

saturated steam by heating through flue gases. This saturated steam is released from the evaporator with a temperature of 1100°C, measured through the temperature gauge placed at the saturated steam outlet. Steam engine Superheaters were engineered to increase efficiency by transforming saturated steam into dry steam. Saturated steam moves from the throttle valve through the dry pipe into the superheater header attached to the tube sheet in the smoke box. This steam then passes through elements which are housed in the superheater flues. Combustible gasses from the firebox move through the tubes and heat the water and the steam inside of the super heater element. By this saturated steam converted into superheated steam with 14000°C temperature and 1.5 bar pressure. At the end of its cycle through the elements, it proceeds into a separate compartment of the superheater header into the distribution pipes, then on to the piston valves and then onto the main steam cylinders. Superheaters are more expensive and require extra maintenance however the benefits as a result of application of dampers are reduced water and fuel consumption. Superheater reliability, safety and usability are crucial for power plants. Superheaters and channels have a limited lifespan; therefore, preventive condition monitoring is very important. The right action to be taken at the right time in optimizing the use of superheater requires preventing leaks, accidents and interruptions for the sake of safety, the environment and maximal uptime.

4.1 Calculations

4.1.1 Heat Supplied To Super Heater:

Table 4.1: Operating Data of the Superheater of the Boiler in the Production Plant (NBC Plc, 2006a)

S/NO	DESCRIPTION	SYMBOL	VALUE	UNIT
1.	Super heated steam outlet temperature	T_1	200	°C
2.	Saturated steam inlet temperature	T_2	170	°C
3.	Flue gases inlet temperature	T_{fi}	350	°C
4.	Flue gases outlet temperature	T_{fo}	230	°C
5.	Initial temperature difference= $(T_{fi}-T_2)$	ITD	230	°C
6	Terminal temperature difference= $(T_{fo}-T_1)$	TTD	30	°C

Table 4.2: Operating Data of the Superheater of the Boiler in the Production Plant (NBC Plc, 2006a) Cont'd.

S/NO	DESCRIPTION	SYMBOL	VALUE	UNIT
1.	Steam flow considered	W	30	Kg/hr
2.	Saturated steam inlet temperature	T_s	100	°C
3.	Superheated steam enthalpy	λ_1	674.502 8	Kcal/k g
4.	Enthalpy of saturated steam	λ_2	636.400	Kcal/k g
5.	Heat to be supplied to superheater	Q	1262.110	Kcal/h r

Heat to be supplied to super heater $Q = (\lambda_1 - \lambda_2) \times W = (674.5028-636.400) \times 30 \text{ kg/hr} = 1143.1 \text{ kcal/kg}$

Table 4.3: TTD Calculation: Overall Heat Transfer Coefficient” U” Calculation On Cleanliness Factor

S/NO	DESCRIPTION	SYMBOL	VALUE	UNIT
1.	Uncorrected heat transfer coefficient	U_1	1663.9	Kcal/m ² h ⁰ C
2.	Inlet water temperature correction factor	F_w	0.825	
3.	Tube material & gauge correction factor	F_m	0.75	
4.	Cleanliness factor	F_c	0.6430	
5.	Overall heat transfer coefficient= $U=U_1 \times F_w \times F_m \times F_c$	U	669.93	Kcal/m ² h ⁰ C

Table 4.4: Surface Area Calculation of Superheater of the Boiler in the Production Plant (NBC Plc, 2006a)

S/NO	DESCRIPTION	SYMBOL	VALUE	UNIT
1.	Heat to be supplied to super heater	Q	1250.110	Kcal/hr
2.	Overall heat transfer co-efficient	U	705.70	Kcal/m ² h
3.	Terminal temperature difference	TTD	35.00	⁰ C
4.	Total area required= $Q/(U \times TTD)$	A	0.05	m ²

Table 4.5: Tube Diameter and Area Calculation of Superheater of the Boiler in the Production Plant (NBC Plc, 2006a)

S/NO	DESCRIPTION	SYMBOL	VALUE	UNIT
1.	Tube outside diameter	D_o	26	mm
2.	Tube inside diameter	D_i	20	mm
3.	Length of tube considered	L	1180	mm
4.	Area considered $A = \pi D_o L$	A	0.09	mm

Design margin considered = 55.53 %

4.2 Results of Assessment of Critical Operational Parameters of the Boiler System

These values can be determined by using measuring and calibrated instruments fitted to the boiler providing the following data on fuel and combustion air temperature, temperature and pressure of feed-water entering boiler, the superheated steam temperature and pressure leaving the boiler and flow rates of feed water into the boiler, recorded daily by the plant operators in the production monitoring report of the facility log to guide the operator towards optimizing the efficiency of the boiler. The results revealed that the operational parameters critical to evaluating the thermodynamic performance of boiler system in the oil mill obtained through direct observation, interviews and from operational record of the boiler include:

- i. The mass flow rate of steam 0.3kg/s
- ii. Constant pressure 0.5MPa (5bar)
- iii. Superheated temperature 195⁰C (468K)
- iv. Saturated temperature 54⁰C (327K)
- v. Enthalpy of superheated steam leaving the boiler 2844.3736kJ/kg
- vi. Enthalpy of feed water entering the boiler 225.848kJ/kg
- vii. The dry column concentration of the CO₂
- viii. The dry column concentration of the CO

4.3 Results of Combustion Efficiency Analysis of Boiler in NBC Plc Production Plant.

The results from the combustion efficiency analysis of the boiler system in NBC Plc’s was also computed as seen in Appendix III and presented in Table 4.3.

Table 4.6 Summary of Results from the Boiler Combustion Efficiency Analysis

Day	Superheated Steam Temperature, K	Combustion Efficiency, %
1	468	83.33
2	466	81.97
3	461	80.65
4	459	79.37
5	452	78.13

Figure 4.1 shows the relationship between boiler combustion efficiency and superheated steam temperature of the boiler.

Figure 4.1: Boiler Combustion Efficiency against Superheated Steam Temperature

The graph shows that the boiler combustion efficiency is directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the oil mill. In other words, the graph shows that as the superheated steam temperature of the boiler increases, the boiler combustion efficiency increases and vice versa. The illustration revealed that there exists a very strong correlation (correlation coefficient (r = 0.952) between the boiler combustion efficiency and superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the oil mill.

4.4 Results of Energy Analysis of Boiler in NBC Plc Plant

The results of the energy analysis for the thermodynamic performance evaluation of the boiler system in NBC Plc’s production plant was also computed as seen in Appendix III as well as using MATLAB computer codes (See Appendix 1) and presented in Table 4.7.

Table 4.7: Analysis of Results from the Boiler Energy Analysis

Day	Superheated Steam Temperature, K	Energy Transfer, kW	Energy Efficiency, %
1	468	785.5577	37.59
2	466	784.2129	37.52
3	461	780.8509	37.36
4	459	779.7995	37.29
5	452	774.7995	37.07

Figure 4.2 shows the relationship between energy transfer in boiler and superheated steam temperature of the boiler.

Figure 4.2: Energy Transfer in Boiler against Superheated Steam Temperature

The graph shows that energy transfer in boiler is directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the oil mill. In other words, the graph shows that as the superheated steam temperature of the boiler increases, the energy transfer in boiler increases and vice versa. The illustration revealed that there exist a very strong correlation (correlation coefficient ($r = 0.999$)) between the energy transfer in boiler and superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant.

Figure 4.3 shows the relationship between the energy efficiency of the boiler against superheated steam temperature of the boiler.

Figure 4.3: Energy Efficiency of Boiler against Superheated Steam Temperature

The graph shows that energy efficiency of the boiler is directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the oil mill. In other words, the graph shows that as the superheated steam temperature of the boiler increases, the energy efficiency of the boiler increases as well and vice versa. The illustration revealed that there exist a very strong correlation (correlation coefficient ($r = 0.999$)) between the energy efficiency of the boiler against superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the oil mill.

Figure 4.4 shows the relationship between the energy efficiency of boiler against energy transfer in boiler.

Figure 4.4: Energy Efficiency of Boiler against Energy Transfer in Boiler

The graph shows that energy efficiency of the boiler is directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant. In other words, the graph shows that as the energy transfer in boiler increases, the energy efficiency of boiler increases as well and vice versa. The illustration revealed that there exists a very strong correlation (correlation coefficient, $r = 0.998$) between the energy efficiency of boiler against energy transfer in boiler in the oil mill.

4.5 Results of Exergy Analysis of Boiler in NBC Plc production plant

The results of the exergy analysis for the thermodynamic performance evaluation of the boiler system in NBC Plc production plant was also computed as seen in Appendix III as well as using MATLAB computer codes (See Appendix 1) and presented in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Analysis of Results from the Boiler Exergy Analysis

Day	Superheated Steam Temperature, K	Exergy Destruction, kW	Exergy Efficiency, %
1	468	545.025	44.53
2	466	540.239	44.19
3	461	526.90072	45.18
4	459	521.45093	45.38
5	452	558.6841	46.15

Figure 4.5 shows the relationship between exergy destruction in boiler and superheated steam temperature of the boiler.

Figure 4.5: Exergy Destruction in Boiler against Superheated Steam Temperature

The graph shows that energy transfer in boiler is directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the plant. In other words, the graph shows that as the superheated steam temperature of the boiler increases, the exergy destruction in boiler increases and vice versa. The illustration revealed that there exists a very weak correlation (correlation coefficient ($r = 0.062$)) between the exergy destruction in boiler and superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the plant.

Figure 4.6 shows the relationship between the exergy efficiency of the boiler against superheated steam temperature of the boiler.

Figure 4.6: Exergy Efficiency of Boiler against Superheated Steam Temperature

The graph shows that exergy efficiency of the boiler is directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant. In other words, the graph shows that as the superheated steam temperature of the boiler increases, the exergy efficiency of the boiler increases as well and vice versa. The illustration revealed that there exists a very strong correlation (correlation coefficient ($r = 0.924$)) between the exergy efficiency of the boiler against superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant.

Figure 4.7 shows the relationship between the exergy efficiency of boiler against exergy destruction in the boiler.

Figure 4.7: Exergy Efficiency of Boiler against Exergy Destruction in Boiler

The graph shows that exergy efficiency of the boiler is directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant. In other words, the graph shows that as the exergy destruction in boiler increases, the exergy efficiency of boiler increases as well and vice versa. The illustration revealed that there exists a very weak correlation (correlation coefficient, $r = 0.050$) between the exergy efficiency of boiler against exergy destruction in boiler in the production plant.

The thermodynamic performance of the boiler system in a production plant targeted at improving its efficiency has been carried. The results are analyzed for the operational parameters critical to evaluating the thermodynamic performance of boiler system in the production plant, the combustion analysis so as to ascertain the combustion products of the fuel and combustion efficiency of the boiler's fuel system, the energy transfer and energy efficiency of the boiler system in the production plant, as well as the exergy efficiency and the exergy destruction of the boiler system for its performance improvement.

From the analysis, the results revealed that the operational parameters critical to evaluating the thermodynamic performance of boiler system in the production plant obtained through direct observation, interviews and from operational record of the boiler include the mass flow rates, pressures, temperatures and enthalpies of the working fluid for a period of five (5) days. The dry column concentration of CO_2 measured after combustion was 10ppmv throughout the 5 days and the dry column concentration of CO measured for the 5 days after combustion were 2.0, 2.2, 2.4, 2.6 and 2.8ppmv with values of superheated steam temperatures: 468K, 466K, 461K, 459K, and 452K generated respectively after heating. The result for the combustion analysis showed that, in practice, excess air beyond the theoretical air was added to the combustion process, for stoichiometric combustion products such as CO_2 , H_2O and N_2 to is achieved. The combustion efficiency of the boiler system in the oil mill was analysed for five (5) consecutive days with different values of superheated steam temperatures: 468K, 466K, 461K, 459K, and 452K respectively. The combustion efficiencies of the boiler (CE) determined for 5 days with different superheated steam temperatures: 468K, 466K, 461K, 459K, and 452K were 83.3%, 81.97%, 80.65%, 79.37% and 78.13% respectively. The energy transfer rate and energy efficiency of the boiler system in the production plant were analysed for five (5) consecutive days with different values of superheated steam temperatures: 468K, 466K, 461K, 459K, and 452K respectively. The energy transfers rates in the boiler analyzed for the 5 days with different superheated steam temperatures: 468K, 466K, 461K, 459K, and 452K were 784.556kW, 784.213kW, 780.851kW, 779.799kW and 774.799kW respectively. And the energy efficiencies of the boiler analyzed for the 5 days with different superheated steam temperatures: 468K, 466K, 461K, 459K, and 452K were 37.59%, 37.52%, 37.36%, 37.29% and 37.07% respectively. The exergy destruction and exergy efficiency of the boiler system in the production plant were analysed for five (5) consecutive days with different values of superheated steam temperatures: 468K, 466K, 461K, 459K, and 452K respectively. The exergy destruction rates in the boiler analyzed for the 5 days with different superheated steam temperatures: 468K, 466K, 461K, 459K, and 452K were 545.025kW, 540.239kW, 526.901kW, 521.451kW and 558.684kW respectively. And the exergy efficiencies of the boiler analyzed for the 5 days with different superheated steam temperatures: 468K, 466K, 461k, 459k, and 452k were 44.53%, 44.19%, 45.18%, 45.38% and 46.157% respectively.

The relationship between the energy transfer in boiler and superheated steam temperature of the boiler, the energy efficiency of the boiler and superheated steam temperature of the boiler, the energy efficiency of boiler and energy transfer in boiler, the exergy destruction in boiler and superheated steam temperature of the boiler, the exergy efficiency of the boiler and superheated steam temperature of the boiler and the exergy efficiency of boiler against exergy destruction in the boiler were investigated. The result showed that the energy transfer in boiler and the energy efficiency of the boiler are directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant. In other words, the result showed that as the superheated steam temperature of the boiler increases, the energy transfer and the energy efficiency of the boiler increases and vice versa. The analysis revealed that there exist a very strong correlation (correlation coefficient ($r = 0.999$)) between the energy transfer and the energy efficiency of the boiler and superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant.

The relationship between the energy efficiency of boiler against energy transfer in boiler as assessed showed that energy efficiency of the boiler is directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant. In other words, the result showed that as the energy transfer in boiler increases, the energy efficiency of boiler increases as well and vice versa. The analysis revealed that there exist a very strong correlation (correlation coefficient, $r = 0.998$) between the energy efficiency of boiler against energy transfer in boiler in the production plant. The result showed that the exergy destruction in boiler and the exergy efficiency of the boiler are directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant. In other words, the result showed that as the superheated steam temperature of the boiler increases, the exergy destruction and the exergy efficiency of the boiler increases and vice versa. The analysis revealed that there exist a very weak

correlation (correlation coefficient ($r = 0.063$) between the exergy destruction in boiler and the exergy efficiency of the boiler while there exist a very strong correlation (correlation coefficient ($r = 0.924$) between the exergy efficiency of the boiler against superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant.

The relationship between the exergy efficiency of boiler against exergy destruction in the boiler as investigated showed that exergy efficiency of the boiler is directly proportional to the superheated steam temperature of the boiler in the production plant. In other words, the result showed that as the exergy destruction in boiler increases, the exergy efficiency of boiler increases as well and vice versa. The analysis revealed that there exist a very weak correlation (correlation coefficient, $r = 0.050$) between the exergy efficiency of boiler against exergy destruction in boiler in the production plant. These results are in agreement with results gotten in previous studies (Igboanugo et al., 2013; Patel & Modi, 2015; Nishant et al., 2018; Krishan et al., 2014; Ukpaka et al., 2019).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The above experiment shows how tube failure can be arrested by using manual damper. In huge power plants tube failure in super heaters can be arrested by de-superheater, which controls the steam temperature by spraying water droplets through nozzle on surface. Here, manual damper controls the flue gases temperature, further arresting tube failure. By increasing tube area, tube failure can be arrested. Total tube area required is 0.05 m^2 by considering some design margin 55.53% tube area increased to 0.09 m^2 , therefore by increasing tube area and by using manual damper, tube failure can be arrested and thereby improving the overall performance of the boiler system.

Recommendations for Future Studies

Based on the results and findings of this research, the following recommendations are proffered to improve the performance of the boiler system in the production plant:

- i. The Government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and the Nigerian Bottling Company (NBC) Plc should assist in making provision for grants and funds for Universities and scholar to facilitate more research of this peculiarity as finance was a major limitation of this study.
- ii. The exergy destruction and exergy efficiency of the boiler depends significantly on the temperature of the superheated steam in the boiler. Low exergy efficiency is a consequence of high exergy destruction rate of the boiler in the production plant, and as such should be considered in improving the boiler performance.
- iii. Further research bordering on assessing the overall performance of a boiler system with the use of manual damper fabricated and designed to be used as a desuperheater in place of a superheater, as there are limited researches on this area.

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